

FACTORS AFFECTING QUALITY EDUCATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING STRATEGIES AMONG FACULTY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN SULU

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study assesses the factors affecting quality education and effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during the Academic Year 2022-2023. Adopting purposive sampling method with 200 samples, wherein data were analyzed by using weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r , this study reveals the following findings: 1) Majority are female, within 20-30 years old, are married in status, have 3-10 of length of service, have Instructor rank, and have master's degree. 2) Teacher-respondents affirmed that school culture, teachers' attitude, teachers' skills, teachers' commitments, and teachers' performance are significant factors that affect the delivery of quality education in public HEIs in Sulu. 3) Teacher-respondents affirmed that there is a high extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public HEIs in Sulu. College faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent in the use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. They are effective in selecting different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources. 4) On the average, there is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to gender, age, civil status, length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment. 5) On the average, there is no significant difference in the extent of teaching strategies of faculty in public HEIs in Sulu when data are categorized according to gender, age, civil status, length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment. 6) There is a high correlation between factors affecting quality education and teaching strategies among public HEIs in Sulu. That is, faculty of HEIs in Sulu who generally perceived the extent of

factors affecting quality education as “Agree” are most probably the same group of faculty who perceived the extent of teaching strategies “Agree” or with high extent, respectively.

Keywords: *Quality Education, Teaching strategies, Higher Education Institutions*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental pillar that shapes individuals and societies, equipping them with essential knowledge, skills, and principles to navigate an ever-evolving world (Schleicher, 2018). Ensuring the provision of high-quality education is of paramount importance, necessitating a comprehensive examination of the factors that influence its delivery and the effectiveness of teaching strategies employed by faculty members in institutions of higher education.

The province of Sulu, located in the Philippines, is home to numerous esteemed higher education institutions dedicated to providing exceptional educational opportunities to their students. However, similar to other educational environments, these establishments face various challenges that can impact the quality of education and the efficacy of the pedagogical approaches used by their faculty (Arcelo, 2003).

The objective of this case study is to examine and assess the factors that influence the quality of teaching at higher education institutions in Sulu. Specifically, the researchers aim to evaluate the effectiveness of the instructional methods employed by the faculty. By identifying these crucial elements, the researchers seek to acquire valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the existing educational system, ultimately formulating strategies to enhance the overall quality of instruction in the region.

This study is underpinned by an extensive review of relevant literature, supplemented by interviews with faculty members and surveys administered to students. The outcomes of this research will not only benefit the faculty and educational administrators in Sulu, but they will also offer significant perspectives for policymakers and educators in comparable settings (Banerjee & Duflo, 2014; Darling-Hammond, 2000).

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the Faculty of Public Higher Education Institutions in Sulu in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Gender;
 - c. Length of Service;
 - d. Educational attainment;
 - e. Academic Rank; and
 - f. Civil Status?

2. What is the extent of the factors affecting Quality Education among Faculty of Higher Education Institutions in Sulu in terms of:
 - a. School Culture;
 - b. Teachers' Attitudes;
 - c. Teachers' skills
 - d. Teachers' commitments and;
 - e. Teachers' Performance

3. What is the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among Faculty of Higher Education Institutions in Sulu in terms of:
 - a. Lecture;
 - b. Modular;
 - c. Online;
 - d. Questioning;
 - e. Discussion;
 - f. Activity-based method;
 - g. Problem-based learning; and
 - h. Simulations?

4. Is there a significant difference on the factors affecting Quality Education Among Faculty of Higher Education Institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to age, gender, length of service, educational attainment, academic rank and civil status?

5. Is there a significant difference in the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies Among Faculty of Higher Education Institutions in Sulu when their responses are grouped according to age, gender, length of service, educational attainment, academic rank and civil status?

6. Is there a significant correlation between leadership attributes and effectiveness of teaching strategies Among Faculty of Higher Education Institutions in Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-exploratory research design with a quantitative approach to investigate the factors influencing the quality of education and the effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members in public higher education institutions in Sulu. The researcher utilized the descriptive research method to carefully examine and describe the educational phenomena in this context.

The study was conducted in five public higher education institutions in Sulu: Sulu State College (SSC), Mindanao State University – Sulu (MSU), Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades (HBSAT), Lapak Agricultural College (LAC), and Lapak National School of Fisheries (LNSF) during the academic year 2022-2023. The total number of respondents included 200 faculty members from these institutions.

To select the sample, the researcher used a purposive sampling method due to access, availability, and time constraints. This method allowed the researcher to purposefully choose representative samples from each institution.

The researcher adopted a survey questionnaire from the studies of Martin Modi (2013) and Nurhuda Alih (2017) to collect data from the faculty respondents. The instrument consisted of three parts:

1. Demographic Profile: This section gathered information on the respondents' age, sex, educational attainment, academic rank, and civil status.

2. Factors Affecting Quality Education: This section assessed the factors affecting quality education in terms of school culture, teachers' attitudes, teachers' skills, teachers' commitments, and teachers' performance. Each component had 10 items measured on a 5-point Likert scale.

3. Effectiveness of Teaching Strategies: This section evaluated the level of effectiveness of various teaching strategies, including lecture, modular, online, questioning, discussion, activity-based, problem-based learning, and simulation. Each teaching strategy had 5 items measured on a 5-point Likert scale.

The 5-point Likert scale ranged from 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Neutral), 2 (Disagree) 1 (Strongly Disagree).

The researcher conducted a pilot test with 20 faculty members not included in the final sample to ensure the reliability and clarity of the instrument.

The collected data was analyzed using various statistical tools, including frequency counts, percentage distributions, weighted means, standard deviations, t-tests, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and Pearson correlation coefficients. These analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software to generate and validate the primary empirical data for the study.

It is important to note that the scope of this study was limited to the five public higher education institutions in Sulu, and the findings may not be generalizable to private institutions or other regions. Additionally, the use of a purposive sampling method may introduce some degree of bias in the representation of the faculty population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter showcases the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data collected for this study. Specifically, it describes the extent of factors affecting quality education and effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sulu during Academic Year 2022-2023.

More specifically, this chapter deals with demographic profiles of faculty-respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, length of service, academic rank, and educational attainment; extent of factors affecting quality education in the context of : School culture, Teachers' attitude, Teachers' skills, Teachers' commitments, and Teachers' performance; and Level of effectiveness of Teaching Strategies in the context of: Lecture, Modular, Online, Questioning, Discussion, Activity-Based Method, Problem-Based Learning, and Simulations; and the significant correlation and differences in these sub-categories when data are classified according to teacher-respondents' demographic profiles.

Consequently, the following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that which correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of: 1.1 Gender, 1.2 Age, 1.3 Length of service, 1.4 Status of appointment, and 1.5 Educational attainment?

1.1 In terms of Gender

Table 1.1 portrays the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of gender. From this table, it can be gleaned that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 135 (67.5%) are female and 65 (32.5%) are male. These data show that nearly three-fourth or majority of the teacher-respondents are female. This result implies that female faculty members of public HEIs in Sulu are bit higher in number as contrasted against their male counterparts.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Teachers	Percent
Male	65	32.5%
Female	135	67.5%
Total	200	100%

1.2 In terms of Age

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of age. From this table, it can be gleaned that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 48 (24.0%) are 20-30 years old, 84 (42.0%) are 31-40 years old , and 68 (34.0%) are 41-65 years old.

These data show that there are nearly one-half of the teacher-respondents are within 20-30 years old. This result implies that there is high concentration or pool of college teachers of HEIs in Sulu into the lowest age brackets as categorized in this study.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of age

Age	Number of Teachers	Percent
20-30 years old	48	24.0%
31-40 years old	84	42.0%
41-65 years old	68	34.0%
Total	200	100%

1.3 In terms of Civil Status

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of civil status. From this table, it can be gleaned that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 40 (20.0%) are Single, 143 (71.5%) are Married, and 17 (8.5%) are Widowed/Separated.

These data show that there is nearly three-fourth or great majority of the teacher-respondents who are married in status. This result implies that the teaching work force of HEIs in Sulu is constituted by married teachers who are assumed to have multiple tasks which to include teaching tasks, household chores, children’s schooling, and other social obligations.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of civil status

Civil Status	Number of Teachers	Percent
Single	40	20.0%
Married	143	71.5%
Widowed/Separated	17	8.5%
Total	200	100%

1.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents of public higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of length of service. From this table, it can be seen that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 101 (50.50%) have 3-10 years, 50 (25.0%) have 11-20 years, and 49 (24.5%) have 21 years & above. In this study, this means that more than one-half or majority of the teacher-respondents have 3-10 of length of service. This result implies that, the faculty force of public HEIs in Sulu constituted by teachers who within the lowest bracket of length of service as categorized in this study.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of length of service

Length of Service	Number of Teachers	Percent
3-10 years	101	50.50%
11-20 years	50	25.0%
21 years & above	49	24.5%
Total	200	100%

1.5 In terms of Academic Rank

Table 1.5 shows the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents of public higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of academic rank. It can be seen from this table that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 126 (63.0%) are Instructor, 51 (25.5%) are Asst. Professor, 22 (11.0%) are Asso. Professor, and 1 (.5%) is Professor. In this study, this means that nearly three-fourth of the teacher-respondents has Instructor rank. This result implies that, majority of the teachers of public HEIs in Sulu have the lowest academic rank as categorized in this study.

Table 1.5 Demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of academic rank

Academic Rank	Number of Teachers	Percent
Instructor	126	63.0%
Asst. Professor	51	25.5%
Asso. Professor	22	11.0%

Professor	1	.5%
Total	200	100%

1.6 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 1.6 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents of public higher education institutions in Sulu in terms of educational attainment. From this table, it can be seen that out of 200 teacher-respondents, 16 (8.0%) have Baccalaureate degree, 55 (27.5%) have Master's degree, 38 (19.0%) have Doctorate degree, 41 (20.0%) With master's units, and 50 (25.0%) With doctoral units. In this study, this means that nearly one-third or majority of the teacher-respondents have master's degree. This result implies that, the faculty force of public HEIs is mostly consisted of teachers who have master's degree. This result implies that faculty force of public HEIs in Sulu is on the rail toward meeting the minimum hiring qualification of at least master's degree.

Table 1.6 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers	Percent
Baccalaureate degree	16	8.0%
Master's degree	55	27.5%
Doctorate degree	38	19.0%
With master's units	41	20.0%
With doctoral units	50	25.0%
Total	200	100%

2. What is the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of: 2.1 School Culture, 2.2 Teachers' Attitude, 2.3 Teachers' Skills, 2.4 Teachers' Commitments, and 2.5 Teachers' Performance?

2.1 In terms of School Culture

Table 2.1 shows the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of School Culture. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.190 with standard deviation of .5540 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high sense of shared beliefs,

perceptions, relationships, attitudes, and morals that shape and influence quality education.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “I have a clear understanding of the ways I can serve as an advocate and champion for our district”, “The planning and organizational time allotted to teachers and staff is used to plan as collective units/teams rather than as separate individuals”, “Teachers and staff work together to develop the school schedule”, “When there's a problem, my district tends to be proactive”, “Teachers and staff are involved in the decision-making process with regard to materials and resources”, “Teachers and staff tell stories of celebrations that support the school’s values”.

But teacher-respondents are rated with “Strongly Agree” on items: “I do a great job of reinforcing and promoting our mission, both internally and externally”, and “We are providing a safe, healthy, and effective learning environment for our students”.

Table 2.1 Extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of School Culture

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 I do a great job of reinforcing and promoting our mission, both internally and externally	4.60	.575	Strongly Agree
2 We are providing a safe, healthy, and effective learning environment for our students.	4.56	.623	Strongly Agree
3 I have a clear understanding of the ways I can serve as an advocate and champion for our district	4.37	.622	Agree
4 The planning and organizational time allotted to teachers and staff is used to plan as collective units/teams rather than as separate individuals.	4.16	.786	Agree
5 Teachers and staff work together to develop the school schedule	4.14	.914	Agree
6 When there's a problem, my district tends to be pro active	3.97	.918	Agree
7 Teachers and staff are involved in the decision-making process with regard to	4.04	.879	Agree

Materials and resources.			
8 Teachers and staff tell stories of celebrations that support the school's values.	4.15	.829	Agree
9 Teachers and staff visit/talk/meet outside of the school to enjoy each other's company.	3.48	1.15	Undecided
10 Our school reflects a true "sense" of community.	4.23	.683	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.190	.5540	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.2 In terms of Teachers' Attitudes

Table 2.2 shows the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Attitudes. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.416 with standard deviation of .5971 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of attitudes toward teaching profession such that they have genuine caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Agree" the following items: "It gives me pleasure if someone adopts/adapts my educational resources", "Sharing enhances my personal and organizational reputation", "Sharing of educational resources increases my profile amongst peers and others", "As a teacher, it is my responsibility to share all educational resources created by me", "Sharing enhances my confidence as I see myself in part of larger community", "I believe that sharing educational materials will encourage others to do so as well", "Sharing of educational resources improves my professional respect", and "Sharing helps me to get feedback".

Table 2.2 Extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Attitudes

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 It gives me pleasure if someone adopts/adapts my educational resources	4.39	.556	Agree
2 Sharing enhances my personal and organizational reputation	4.39	.591	Agree

3 Sharing of educational resources increases my profile amongst peers and others	4.30	.763	Agree
4 As a teacher, it is my responsibility to share all educational resources created by me	4.31	.684	Agree
5 Sharing enhances my confidence as I see myself in part of larger community	4.37	.597	Agree
6 I believe that sharing educational materials will encourage others to do so as well	4.32	.763	Agree
7 Sharing of educational resources improves my professional respect	4.35	.743	Agree
8 Sharing helps me to get feedback	4.25	.749	Agree
9 I lead personally and Professionally by Example	4.60	.559	Agree
10 When I extend help or favour, I do not expect to be reciprocated	4.46	.575	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.416	.5971	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.3 In terms of Teachers' Skills

Table 2.3 shows the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Skills. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.163 with standard deviation of .4074 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of professional skills in communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, empathy and patience. Moreover, teachers are said to have effective skills in engaging classroom presence, value in real-world learning, exchange of best practices and a lifelong love of learning.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Agree" the following items: "Controls temper in conflict situations with peers", "Introduces herself or himself to new people without being told", "Appropriately questions rules that may be unfair", "Compromises in conflict situations by hanging own ideas to reach agreement", "Responds appropriately to peer pressure", "Says nice things about himself or herself when appropriate", "Invites others to join in activities", "Cooperates with peers without prompting", "Receives criticism well", and "Appropriately tells you when he or she thinks you have treated him or her unfairly".

Table 2.3 Extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Skills

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Controls temper in conflict situations with peers.	4.30	.723	Agree
2 Introduces herself or himself to new people without being told.	3.63	1.217	Agree
3 Appropriately questions rules that may be unfair.	4.16	.695	Agree
4 Compromises in conflict situations by hanging own ideas to reach agreement.	4.16	.717	Agree
5 Responds appropriately to peer pressure.	4.26	.626	Agree
6 Says nice things about himself or herself when appropriate.	4.26	.578	Agree
7 Invites others to join in activities.	4.18	.678	Agree
8 Cooperates with peers without prompting.	4.29	.639	Agree
9 Receives criticism well	4.24	.723	Agree
10 Appropriately tells you when he or she thinks you have treated him or her unfairly.	4.18	.574	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.163	.4074	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.4 In terms of Teachers' Commitments

Table 2.4 shows the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Commitments. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.380 with standard deviation of .4349 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of commitment which then considered as the core of their contribution to student achievement and school goals, and in turn in creating quality education. That is, teachers are said to have love for teaching and work with students through building good relationship with them and showing them respect.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following items: “Teachers do not mix their feeling, emotions and personal problems in the profession work”, “Teachers are in teaching profession because of they are sense of loyalty to it”, “Teachers dislike those who hamper the image of teaching”, “Teachers would feel guilty if they left teaching profession”, “Teachers will not change teaching if teachers” offered better working condition and safety in some other sector”, “Teachers would not leave teaching right now because teachers have a sense of obligation to teaching”, and “Changing teaching profession now would be difficult for teachers”.

However, teacher-respondents rated with “Strongly Agree” the items: “Teaching profession is a great deal of personal meaning for teachers”, “Teachers proud to be in their teaching profession”, and “Teaching profession is important to teacher self-image”.

Table 2.4 Extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers’ Commitments

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Teaching profession is a great deal of personal meaning for teachers.	4.57	.515	Strongly Agree
2 Teachers do not mix their feeling, emotions and personal problems in the profession work.	4.41	.718	Agree
3 Teachers are in teaching profession because of they are sense of loyalty to it.	4.48	.576	Agree
4 Teachers dislike those who hamper the image of teaching.	4.34	.622	Agree
5 Teachers would feel guilty if they left teaching profession.	4.14	.912	Agree
6 Teachers will not change teaching if teachers” offered better working condition and safety in some other sector.	4.11	.939	Agree
7 Teachers would not leave teaching right now because teachers have a sense of obligation to teaching.	4.29	.722	Agree
8 Changing teaching profession now would be difficult for teachers.	4.17	.857	Agree
9 Teachers proud to be in their teaching profession	4.68	.499	Strongly Agree

1 Teaching profession is important to 0 teacher self-image.	4.60	.490	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.380	.4349	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

2.5 In terms of Teachers' Performance

Table 2.5 shows the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Performance. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.577 with standard deviation of .3765 which is rated as "Strongly Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of demonstrating impact on students' learning as established through student achievement, observed pedagogical practices.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Strongly Agree" the following items: "We consider teaching as an opportunity of service for students", "We try to develop self-confidence in the students", "We are sympathetic with students who feel difficulty in subject learning", "We treat all students fairly and honestly", "We maintain courteous and respectful approach when we meet with students", "We provide guidance in our spare time to the students in their academic and non-academic affairs", "We pay important role to improve the character of our students", and "We respect the ideas of others and express a willingness to learn from them".

Table 2.5 Extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Teachers' Performance

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 We consider teaching as an opportunity of service for students.	4.54	.538	Strongly Agree
2 We try to develop self-confidence in the students.	4.57	.526	Strongly Agree
3 We are sympathetic with students who feel difficulty in subject learning.	4.50	.634	Strongly Agree
4 We treat all students fairly and honestly.	4.71	.479	Strongly Agree
5 We maintain courteous and respectful approach when we meet with students.	4.63	.484	Strongly Agree

6	We provide guidance in our spare time to the students in their academic and non-academic affairs.	4.61	.489	Strongly Agree
7	We pay important role to improve the character of our students.	4.57	.507	Strongly Agree
8	We respect the ideas of others and express a willingness to learn from them.	4.63	.524	Strongly Agree
9	We have a sense of humour.	4.52	.618	Strongly Agree
10	We change class procedure to maintain our student's attention, interest and to attempt to reach students varying learning styles.	4.51	.521	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.577	.3765	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3. What is the Level of Effectiveness of Teaching Strategies among faculty of public higher education in Sulu in terms of: 3.1 Lecture, 3.2 Modular, 3.3 Online, 3.4 Questioning, 3.5 Discussion, 3.6 Activity-Based Method, 3.7 Problem-Based Learning, and 3.8 Simulations?

3.1 In terms of Lecture

Table 3.1 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Lecture. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.4360 with standard deviation of .43549 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of lecture.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Agree" the following item: "The teacher is less intellectually demanding for student and teacher".

However, respondents rated with "Strongly Agree" the following items: "The Teacher focuses in teaching on his/her lecture", "Concentrates on the subject that specifies syllabus", "Lectures are a time-efficient way to learn", and "The lecture format is a comfortable way to learn".

Table 3.1 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Lecture

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 The Teacher focuses in teaching on his/her lecture	4.62	.507	Strongly Agree
2 The teacher is less intellectually demanding for student and teacher	4.09	.843	Agree
3 Concentrates on the subject that specifies syllabus	4.51	.521	Strongly Agree
4 Lectures are a time-efficient way to learn	4.49	.530	Strongly Agree
5 The lecture format is a comfortable way to learn	4.47	.548	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.4360	.43549	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.2 In terms of Modular

Table 3.2 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Modular. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3220 with standard deviation of .47056 which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of modular.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following item: “Teacher let students view an interactive power point prior to participating in a group discussion”, “Teacher let students to read and respond to text content in self-selected sub-groups”, “Teacher requires students to read their assign text and respond individually to questions at the end of the text”, “Teacher requires students to read their group’s assigned teach and create a group video or digital photography project demonstrating the context of the assign text”, and “Teachers require students to read and discuss the context in assigned groups”/

Table 3.2 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Modular

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Teacher let students view an interactive power point prior to participating in a group discussion	4.27	.685	Agree
2 Teacher let students to read and respond to text content in self-selected sub-groups.	4.32	.565	Agree
3 Teacher requires students to read their assign text and respond individually to questions at the end of the text.	4.35	.545	Agree
4 Teacher requires students to read their group's assigned teach and create a group video or digital photography project demonstrating the context of the assign text	4.29	.547	Agree
5 Teachers require students to read and discuss the context in assigned groups.	4.38	.545	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.3220	.47056	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.3 In terms of Online

Table 3.3 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Online. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3220 with standard deviation of .47056 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of online teaching.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Agree" the following item: "Before the live class, students answer question's independently", "Teacher uses chat to ask and answer questions or to check for understanding", "Teacher flips classroom to stimulate deeper discussion", "Adapting think-pair-share where students given a prompt, broken into group, then placed into breakout rooms", and "Convert the familiar show-and-tell activity into "think, write, and share."

Table 3.3 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Online

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Before the live class, students answer question's independently	4.27	.685	Agree
2 Teacher uses chat to ask and answer questions or to check for understanding	4.32	.565	Agree
3 Teacher flips classroom to stimulate deeper discussion	4.35	.545	Agree
4 Adapting think-pair-share where students given a prompt, broken into group, then placed into breakout rooms.	4.29	.547	Agree
5 Convert the familiar show-and-tell activity into "think, write, and share."	4.38	.545	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.3220	.47056	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.4 In terms of Questioning

Table 3.4 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Online. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3567 with standard deviation of .41806 which is rated as "Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of questioning.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with "Agree" the following item: "Teacher based on a specified objective", "Question is limited to the scope", and "Mode of questioning provokes critical thinking to students".

Table 3.4 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Questioning

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Teacher based on a specified objective	4.43	.516	Agree
2 Question is limited to the scope	4.26	.587	Agree

3 Mode of questioning provokes critical thinking to students	4.38	.614	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.3567	.41806	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.5 In terms of Discussion

Table 3.5 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Discussion. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.4133 with standard deviation of .43473 which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of discussion.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following item: “Teacher is based on intuition and Experience, “Gives times for students to ask question”, and “Uses visual aids, video clips and pictures”.

Table 3.5 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Discussion

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Teacher is based on intuition and Experience	4.33	.626	Agree
2 Gives times for students to ask questions	4.48	.530	Agree
3 Uses visual aids, video clips and pictures	4.43	.545	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.4133	.43473	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.6 In terms of Activity-Based Method

Table 3.6 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Activity-based Method. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.4933 with standard deviation of .49108 which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of adopting activity-based method.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following item: “Students cooperate and work together to accomplish a common task”, “Students interact rather than compete with each other to accomplish a common task”, and “Teacher acts as “consultant” or guide to support student’s learning”.

Table 3.6 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Activity-based Method

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Students cooperate and work together to accomplish a common task	4.54	.519	Strongly Agree
2 Students interact rather than compete with each other to accomplish a common task	4.47	.609	Agree
3 Teacher acts as “consultant” or guide to support student’s learning	4.47	.634	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.4933	.49108	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.7 In terms of Problem-Based Learning

Table 3.7 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Problem-based learning. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3583 with standard deviation of .53773 which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of adopting problem-based learning.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following item: “Learning is driven by challenging, open-ended problems”, “Student’s work is collaborative groups”, and “Teacher acts as a guide rather than knowledge provider”.

Table 3.7 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Problem-based learning

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Learning is driven by challenging, open-ended problems.	4.42	.597	Strongly Agree
2 Student’s work is collaborative groups	4.34	.588	Agree

3 Teacher acts as a guide rather than knowledge provider	4.31	.712	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.3583	.53773	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

3.8 In terms of Simulations

Table 3.8 shows the level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of Siulation. Under this category, teacher-respondents obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3883 with standard deviation of .45054 which is rated as “Agree”. This result indicates that teacher-respondents perceive that faculty of public HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in terms of adopting simulations.

Moreover, under this category, employee-respondents rated with “Agree” the following item: “Students learn psychomotor skills in a safe and controlled setting”, “Learners apply principles and theories they have learned”, and “Educator’s roles are planner, facilitator and debriefed”.

Table 3.8 Level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu in the context of simulations

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1 Students learn psychomotor skills in a safe and controlled setting	4.36	.557	Agree
2 Learners apply principles and theories they have learned	4.39	.498	Agree
3 Educator’s roles are planner, facilitator and debriefed	4.42	.525	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.3883	.45054	Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49=Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49=Undecided; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49=Strongly Disagree

4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to 4.1 Age, 4.2 Gender, 4.3 Civil status, 4.4 Length of service, 4.5 Academic rank, and 4.6 Educational attainment?

4.1 According to Gender

Table 4.1 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. It can be gleaned from this table that except for “Teachers’ Performance” the Mean Differences, t-values, and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, male and female teacher-respondents in this study indeed differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a male teacher-respondent may indeed not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than his female counterparts, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu the fact they vary in gender, yet they indeed differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty’s caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students’ diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students’ creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has indeed significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to gender” is rejected.

Table 4.1 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Male	.6013	.0745	-.51561	-	6.835	.000
	Female	.4429	.0381				
Teachers' Attitude	Male	.3940	.0488	-.26074	-	2.947	.004
	Female	.6581	.0566				
Teachers' Skills	Male	.3404	.0422	-.15561	-	2.565	.011
	Female	.4281	.0368				
Teachers' Commitme	Male	.4035	.0500	-.14889	-	2.291	.023
	Female	.4426	.0381				
Teachers' Performanc	Male	.3344	.0414	-.02821	-	.495	.621
	Female	.3960	.0340				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.2 According to Age

Table 4.2 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in age range, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent who is within the age range of 41-65 years may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than other teacher-respondents whose age within the range of 20 - 30 years and 31- 40 years, or vice versa.

Henceforth, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu the fact they vary in gender, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty's caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant intervention in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to age" is accepted.

Table 4.2 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Between	.737	2	.368	1.203	.303	Not Significant
	Within Groups	60.358	197	.306			
	Total	61.095	199				
Teachers' Attitude	Between	.075	2	.037	.104	.901	Not Significant
	Within Groups	70.894	197	.360			
	Total	70.969	199				
Teachers' Skills	Between	.244	2	.122	.733	.482	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.799	197	.166			
	Total	33.044	199				
Teachers' Commitments	Between	.202	2	.101	.532	.588	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.451	197	.190			
	Total	37.654	199				
Teachers' Performance	Between	.094	2	.047	.330	.720	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.115	197	.143			
	Total	28.209	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.3 According to Civil Status

Table 4.3 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for "Teachers' Performance" the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in marital status, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent who is married may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than other teacher-respondents who are single, separated or widowed, or vice versa.

Henceforth, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu although they vary in civil status, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty's caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable civil status has no significant intervention in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to civil status” is accepted.

Table 4.3 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Between	1.305	2	.653	2.150	.119	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.790	197	.304			
	Total	61.095	199				
Teachers' Attitude	Between	.006	2	.003	.009	.991	Not Significant
	Within Groups	70.962	197	.360			
	Total	70.969	199				
Teachers' Skills	Between	.882	2	.441	2.702	.070	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.161	197	.163			
	Total	33.044	199				
Teachers' Commitments	Between	.411	2	.206	1.088	.339	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.243	197	.189			
	Total	37.654	199				
Teachers' Performance	Between	1.030	2	.515	3.733*	.026	Significant
	Within Groups	27.179	197	.138			
	Total	28.209	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.4 According to Length of Service

Table 4.4 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in number of years of teaching experience, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent who has permanent teaching status may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than other teacher-respondents who have temporary, contractual or part-time status, or vice versa.

Henceforth, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu although they vary in civil status, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty's caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant intervention in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to length of service" is accepted.

Table 4.4 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Between	.807	2	.403	1.318	.270	Not Significant
	Within Groups	60.288	197	.306			
	Total	61.095	199				
Teachers' Attitude	Between	1.026	2	.513	1.445	.238	Not Significant
	Within Groups	69.943	197	.355			
	Total	70.969	199				
Teachers' Skills	Between	.013	2	.006	.038	.963	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.031	197	.168			
	Total	33.044	199				
Teachers' Commitments	Between	.869	2	.434	2.327	.100	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.785	197	.187			
	Total	37.654	199				
Teachers' Performance	Between	.160	2	.080	.563	.570	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.048	197	.142			
	Total	28.209	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.5 According to Academic Rank

Table 4.5 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for "School Culture" and "Teachers' Attitudes" the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories

subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in academic rank, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent who has Professor rank may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than other teacher-respondents who have Instructor, Assistant professor, and Associate Professor ranks, or vice versa.

Henceforth, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu although they vary in academic rank, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty's caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable academic rank of service has no significant intervention in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to academic rank" is accepted.

Table 4.5 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Between	4.474	3	1.491	5.163*	.002	Significant
	Within Groups	56.621	196	.289			
	Total	61.095	199				
Teachers' Attitude	Between	3.308	3	1.103	3.195*	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	67.660	196	.345			
	Total	70.969	199				
Teachers' Skills	Between	.465	3	.155	.933	.426	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.578	196	.166			
	Total	33.044	199				
Teachers' Commitments	Between	1.377	3	.459	2.480	.062	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.277	196	.185			
	Total	37.654	199				
Teachers' Performance	Between	.379	3	.126	.890	.448	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.830	196	.142			
	Total	28.209	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4.6 According to Educational Attainment

Table 4.6 depicts the difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for “Teachers’ Performance” the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05.

This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in level of educational background, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of factors affecting quality education. This result implies that being a teacher-respondent who has doctorate degree may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of factors affecting quality education than other teacher-respondents who have bachelor’s degree, bachelor’s with units in master’s program, master’s degree, and master’s degree with units in doctoral program, or vice versa.

Henceforth, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu although they vary in educational attainment, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of factors affecting quality education. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived in differently ways how college faculty’s caring and kindness, willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom, a sincere sensitivity to the students’ diversity, a motivation to provide meaningful learning experiences for all students, and an enthusiasm for stimulating the students’ creativity.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant intervention in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the extent of factors affecting quality education. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of factors affecting quality education among faculty members of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to educational attainment” is accepted.

Table 4.6 Differences in the extent of factors affecting quality education among higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
School Culture	Between	2.769	4	.692	2.314	.059	Significant
	Within Groups	58.327	195	.299			
	Total	61.095	199				
Teachers' Attitude	Between	.780	4	.195	.542	.705	Significant
	Within Groups	70.188	195	.360			
	Total	70.969	199				
Teachers' Skills	Between	.813	4	.203	1.229	.300	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.231	195	.165			
	Total	33.044	199				
Teachers' Commitments	Between	1.684	4	.421	2.282	.062	Not Significant
	Within Groups	35.970	195	.184			
	Total	37.654	199				
Teachers' Performance	Between	1.773	4	.443	3.270*	.013	Significant
	Within Groups	26.436	195	.136			
	Total	28.209	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5. Is there a significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to 4.1 Age, 4.2 Gender, 4.3 Civil status, 4.4 Length of service, 4.5 Academic rank, and 4.6 Educational attainment?

5.1 According to Gender

Table 5.1 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. It can be gleaned from this table that except for “Modular” and “Online” the Mean Differences, t-values, and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, male and female teacher-respondents in this study do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that being a male teacher-respondent may indeed not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies than his female counterparts, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu the fact they vary in gender, yet they indeed differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of HEIs in Sulu perceived

differently in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to gender” is accepted.

Table 5.1 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to gender

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Male	4.384	.3763	-.07613	-1.159	.248	Not Significant
	Female	4.460	.4605				
Modular	Male	4.150	.3937	-.25368*	-3.682	.000	Significant
	Female	4.404	.4834				
Online	Male	4.015	.4586	-.21721*	-2.734	.007	Significant
	Female	4.232	.5556				
Questioning	Male	4.374	.3886	.02621	.414	.679	Not Significant
	Female	4.348	.4326				
Discussion	Male	4.379	.4925	-.05014	-.763	.446	Not Significant
	Female	4.429	.4049				
Activity-Based	Male	4.497	.4791	.00608	.082	.935	Not Significant
	Female	4.491	.4984				
Problem-Based	Male	4.312	.5331	-.06743	-.830	.408	Not Significant
	Female	4.380	.5405				
Simulations	Male	4.333	.4208	-.08148	-1.199	.232	Not Significant
	Female	4.414	.4633				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.2 According to Age

Table 5.2 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that except for “Modular” and “Discussion” the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that,

generally, though teacher-respondents vary in age range, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that a teacher-respondent whose age within the range of 41-65 years may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies than other teacher-respondents whose age within 20-30 years, and 3-40 years, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu though they vary in age range, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu perceived similarly in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to age” is accepted.

Table 5.2 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Between	1.056	2	.528	2.835	.061	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.685	197	.186			
	Total	37.741	199				
Modular	Between	1.523	2	.761	3.526*	.031	Significant
	Within Groups	42.540	197	.216			
	Total	44.063	199				
Online	Between	.204	2	.102	.354	.702	Not Significant
	Within Groups	56.707	197	.288			
	Total	56.911	199				
Questioning	Between	.680	2	.340	1.965	.143	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.100	197	.173			
	Total	34.780	199				
Discussion	Between	2.014	2	1.007	5.575	.004	Significant
	Within Groups	35.594	197	.181			
	Total	37.609	199				
Activity-Based Method	Between	.749	2	.374	1.561	.212	Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.242	197	.240			
	Total	47.991	199				
Problem-Based Learning	Between	1.228	2	.614	2.149	.119	Not Significant
	Within Groups	56.313	197	.286			
	Total	57.542	199				
Simulations	Between	.350	2	.175	.861	.424	Not Significant
	Within Groups	40.045	197	.203			
	Total	40.395	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.3 According to Civil Status

Table 5.3 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status. It can be gleaned from this table that except for “Lecturer”, “Online” and “Problem-based Learning” the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in civil status, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who is married may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching

strategies than other teacher-respondents who are single, separated or widowed, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu though they vary in marital status, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu perceived similarly in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable civil status has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to civil status” is accepted.

Table 5.3 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to civil status

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Between	3.007	2	1.504*	8.529	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	34.733	197	.176			
	Total	37.741	199				
Modular	Between	.040	2	.020	.089	.915	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.024	197	.223			
	Total	44.063	199				
Online	Between	2.519	2	1.260*	4.562	.012	Significant
	Within Groups	54.392	197	.276			
	Total	56.911	199				
Questioning	Between	.520	2	.260	1.496	.226	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.260	197	.174			
	Total	34.780	199				
Discussion	Between	.796	2	.398	2.131	.121	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.813	197	.187			
	Total	37.609	199				
Activity-Based Method	Between	.681	2	.341	1.418	.245	Not Significant
	Within Groups	47.310	197	.240			
	Total	47.991	199				
Problem-Based Learning	Between	2.098	2	1.049	3.728	.026	Significant
	Within Groups	55.443	197	.281			
	Total	57.542	199				
Simulations	Between	1.047	2	.524	2.622	.075	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.348	197	.200			
	Total	40.395	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.4 According to Length of Service

Table 5.4 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service. It can be gleaned from this table that except for "Lecturer", "Modular" and "Discussion" the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in length of service, in this study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has been in teaching profession for 21 years & above may not probably make him better

perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies than other teacher-respondents who have been in service for 3-10 years and 11-20 years, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu though they vary in length of service, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu perceived similarly in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable length of service has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to length of service" is accepted.

Table 5.4 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to length of service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Between	4.497	2	2.249	13.325*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	33.244	197	.169			
	Total	37.741	199				
Modular	Between	3.917	2	1.959	9.612*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	40.146	197	.204			
	Total	44.063	199				
Online	Between	.987	2	.494	1.739	.178	Not Significant
	Within Groups	55.924	197	.284			
	Total	56.911	199				
Questioning	Between	.444	2	.222	1.275	.282	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.336	197	.174			
	Total	34.780	199				
Discussion	Between	1.987	2	.993	5.494*	.005	Significant
	Within Groups	35.622	197	.181			
	Total	37.609	199				
Activity-Based Method	Between	1.042	2	.521	2.186	.115	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.949	197	.238			
	Total	47.991	199				
Problem-Based Learning	Between	.442	2	.221	.762	.468	Not Significant
	Within Groups	57.100	197	.290			
	Total	57.542	199				
Simulations	Between	.885	2	.443	2.207	.113	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.510	197	.201			
	Total	40.395	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.5 According to Academic Rank

Table 5.5 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank. It can be gleaned from this table that except for “Modular” and “Online” the F-values and Probability-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in academic rank, in this is study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has Professor rank may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies than

other teacher-respondents who have Instructor, Assistant Professor, and Associate Professor ranks, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu though they vary in academic rank, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu perceived similarly in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable academic rank has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to academic rank” is accepted.

Table 5.5 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to academic rank

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Between	.065	3	.022	.113	.952	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.675	196	.192			
	Total	37.741	199				
Modular	Between	2.665	3	.888	4.206*	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	41.398	196	.211			
	Total	44.063	199				
Online	Between	2.464	3	.821	2.956*	.034	Significant
	Within Groups	54.447	196	.278			
	Total	56.911	199				
Questioning	Between	.564	3	.188	1.077	.360	Not Significant
	Within Groups	34.216	196	.175			
	Total	34.780	199				
Discussion	Between	.581	3	.194	1.024	.383	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.028	196	.189			
	Total	37.609	199				
Activity-Based Method	Between	1.627	3	.542	2.293	.079	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.364	196	.237			
	Total	47.991	199				
Problem-Based Learning	Between	2.231	3	.744	2.635	.051	Not Significant
	Within Groups	55.311	196	.282			
	Total	57.542	199				
Simulations	Between	.738	3	.246	1.216	.305	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.657	196	.202			
	Total	40.395	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

5.6 According to Educational Attainment

Table 5.6 depicts the difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-values and Probability-values of all sub-categories subsumed under the extent of factors affecting quality education are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, generally, though teacher-respondents vary in level of educational background, in this is study they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. This result implies that a teacher-respondent who has doctorate degree may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies than

other teacher-respondents who have bachelor's degree, bachelor's with MA units, master's degree, and master's degree with doctoral units, or vice versa.

Moreover, it can be inferred further that teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu though they vary in educational attainment, yet they do not differ in ways of perceiving the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies. That is, teachers of public HEIs in Sulu perceived similarly in ways how college faculty use instructional methods to deliver course materials in ways that keep students engaged and practicing different skills sets. That is, how instructors select different teaching strategies according to unit topic, year level, class size, and classroom instructional resources.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable educational attainment has no significant influence in ways how teachers of higher education institutions in Sulu perceive the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty members of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are classified according to educational attainment" is accepted.

Table 5.6 Differences in the extent of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu when data are grouped according to educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Lecture	Between	.778	4	.195	1.027	.395	Not Significant
	Within Groups	36.962	195	.190			
	Total	37.741	199				
Modular	Between	1.743	4	.436	2.008	.095	Not Significant
	Within Groups	42.320	195	.217			
	Total	44.063	199				
Online	Between	.686	4	.171	.594	.667	Not Significant
	Within Groups	56.226	195	.288			
	Total	56.911	199				
Questioning	Between	1.512	4	.378	2.216	.069	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.268	195	.171			
	Total	34.780	199				
Discussion	Between	.509	4	.127	.669	.614	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.099	195	.190			
	Total	37.609	199				
Activity-Based Method	Between	1.463	4	.366	1.533	.194	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.528	195	.239			
	Total	47.991	199				
Problem-Based Learning	Between	.573	4	.143	.490	.743	Not Significant
	Within Groups	56.969	195	.292			
	Total	57.542	199				
Simulations	Between	.997	4	.249	1.233	.298	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.398	195	.202			
	Total	40.395	199				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

6. Is there a significant correlation between factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu?

Table 6 illustrates the correlation between factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu.

Specifically, the degrees of correlations correlation between factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu is as follows:

- 1) High positive correlation between factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu.

This result indicates that the teachers of public higher education institutions in Sulu who generally perceived the extent factors affecting quality education as “Agree” are most probably the same group of teachers who perceived the extent of coping strategies as “Agree”, respectively.

Meanwhile, it is safe to say that, generally the extent of teachers’ perceptions factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu is highly correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant correlation between factors affecting quality education and level of effectiveness of teaching strategies among faculty of public higher education institutions in Sulu” is rejected.

Table 6. Correlation between work-related stress and coping strategies

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Factors Affecting Quality Education	Effectiveness of Teaching Strategies	.676**	.000	200	High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

This study forwards the conclusions:

- 1) There is sufficient representation of faculty of HEIs in Sulu in terms of gender, age, civil status, length of service, status of appointment, and educational attainment.
- 2) On the average, the delivery quality education among public HEIs in Sulu is affected by school culture, teachers’ attitude, teachers’ skills, teachers’ commitments, and teachers’ performance.
- 3) On the average, faculty members of HEIs in Sulu have high extent of effectiveness in adopting teaching strategies.
- 4) College faculty members do not differ in ways of assessing the factors affecting quality education in public HEIs in Sulu.
- 5) Generally, college faculty members do not differ in ways of assessing teachers’ teaching strategies in public HEIs in Sulu.

6) The constructs of factors affecting quality education and teaching strategies is highly correlated.

Recommendations

This study recommends that:

1) Administrators of HEIs in Sulu should continue implementing programs and policies that would minimize the delivery of quality education.

2) Administrators of HEIs in Sulu should continue to support teachers in addressing issues and concerns pertaining to effective delivery of quality education in tertiary level.

3) Administrators and heads of academic departments should continue extending their support to college faculty members so that their pedagogical knowledge and skills could be enhanced.

4) More trainings on updated pedagogy such as effective teaching approaches, methods and procedures should be conducted among college faculty members in HEIs in Sulu.

5) Student-researchers in the field of educational administration are encouraged to conduct study similar to this one but to include other variables such as teachers' anxiety, teachers' morale, and teaching performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study was conducted with the highest level of ethical standards and integrity. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained the necessary approvals and informed consent from the relevant authorities and the participants involved. The faculty members who participated in this study were informed of the purpose and nature of the research, and their voluntary participation was solicited. Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and the anonymity of their identities, and they were made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

The well-being and safety of the participants were of utmost importance throughout the research process. The researcher ensured that no harm, either physical or psychological, was caused to the respondents during their involvement in the study. Furthermore, the researcher declares that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this research, and all data collected and analyzed were handled with the highest level of objectivity and free from bias. The content of this research is the original work of the researcher, and any contributions or references made to external sources have been properly acknowledged and cited in accordance with academic standards.

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